

Gangotri Gomukh and its retreat in Google Earth time series 2010-2022

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In 2017, we considered the retreat of the Gangotri Gomukh, the terminus of the Gangotri Glacier. This is a Himalayan glacier located in the Uttarkashi District, India. Further investigation is today necessary about the rate of retreating Gomukh I proposed in 2017. The rate had been obtained by means of Google Earth satellite images of 2010 and 2016. Here we consider a different approach, using the satellite images of 2010 and 2017, and Google Earth tools. The use of Google Earth images of 2019 and 2022 is also suggested.

Keywords: Satellite imagery, Glacier terminus retreat, Gangotri glacier.

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In 2017, we used a time series of satellite images in Google Earth for measuring the retreat of the terminus of Gangotri Glacier, one of the largest glaciers of Himalayas. The terminus of the Gangotri Glacier is also known as Gomukh, the “Mouth of the Cow”, due the shape of its profile. From the Gomukh, the Bhagirathi River originates, which is one of the main tributaries of the Ganges River. For this reason, the Gomukh is also a place of pilgrimages. As for other glaciers, the terminus of Gangotri moves due to the environmental conditions and its shape is continuously changing.

About the studies on Gomukh, in 2017 we mentioned Bahuguna et al., 2007, Bhambri et al., 2012, Drew, 2012, Naithani et al., 2001, Mukherjee and Sangewar, 2001, Raina, 2004 and Vohra, 1981. In Raina, 2004, according to a series of historical data, it was concluded that the retreat of the Gomukh was of 15 to 18 meters per year, and then “definitely not alarming. Some of the glaciers in Columbia and even in Alaska have recently shown an annual retreat of more than 200 metres”. The data given by Raina agree to those in Bhambri et al., 2012. In this last reference, the researchers reported the frontal area changes at the terminus of Gangotri Glacier, after a work based on high-resolution satellite data from 1965 to 2006. The results show that the glacier exhibited a retreat up to 819 ± 14 m (it means about 20 m/yr). Other retreat rates are 15, 19 and 40 meters per year, given in Vohra, 1981, Naithani et al., 2001, and Mukherjee and Sangewar, 2001. In Bahuguna et al., 2007, we can also find the data by WWF of a mean rate per year of 28 m. Besides these articles, let us also add Saraswat et al., 2013. “Results show that on average, the Gangotri glacier snout has receded at a rate of 21.3 ± 3 m year⁻¹ over a period of 6 years (2004–2010)”.

In Yousuf et al., March 2024, we can find a Table reporting retreat measurements of Gangotri. “Slight or considerable differences exist among the estimated retreat values and few reported ones for near or same duration. These differences are mainly due to the data/approaches/observational period considered in these studies. The super-resolution derived retreat rate of the Gangotri glacier during 2010–2016 is 1.72-fold lower than that estimated by Sparavigna (2017), but similar to Bisht et al.’s (2020) estimates. Sparavigna (2017) just used a common reference point with same position in the two Google Earth images (2010 and 2016) to measure the displacement of the glacier terminus, leading to retreat overestimation. However, manual derivation of retreat rates using the same Google Earth images (16.62 ± 13.02 m a⁻¹) confirm relatively low glacier retreat rate during this period” (Yousuf et al., 2024).

We need therefore to show again what we did in 2017, using the images proposed today (March 2024) by the time series of Google Earth. In fact, we can see also that satellite images are available until 2022. Since a difference of retreat rate exists, between my result given in 2017 and Yousuf and coworkers result proposed in 2024, it is fundamental to understand how Google Earth is showing the satellite maps and what are the

measurements that we can obtain by means of the tools available in this software. Yousuf and coworkers have not considered the images from 2016 to 2022; a comparison of the rates during 2010–2016 and during 2016–2022, could give relevant information about the effect of the global warming on Gangotri Glacier.

Before approaching Google Earth images, let us consider some further literature. Bisht and coworkers, 2020, monitored Gangotri Glacier during the ablation season, from May to September, in years 2005 and 2015, “by using rapid static and kinematic GPS survey”. The survey “reveals that the retreating rate has been comparatively more declined than shown by the earlier studies”. “The GPS dataset show that the total average retreat along the snout has been 102.57 ± 0.05 m from 2005 to 2015 with an average rate as 10.26 ± 0.05 m/yr. Additionally, the shift in snout position was also measured through multi-temporal satellite data from 1989 to 2016. The results indicate that the Gangotri glacier snout has retreated by 585.62 ± 38.30 m during this period with an average retreat of 26.75 ± 4.36 m/yr from 1989 to 1999, 21.58 ± 3.77 m/yr from 1999 to 2009 and 14.60 ± 4.81 m/yr from 2009 to 2016. Such a decline in retreat is further confirmed by the satellite data set” (Bisht et al, 2020).

Bhambri et al., 2023, proposed a study of the frontal retreat of Gangotri Glacier between 1935 and 2022. The researchers used a “large scale Geological Survey of India map, remote sensing images, and repeated photography. Gangotri Glacier's retreat rate varied significantly during the study period. This glacier receded by 1727 ± 51 m (19.8 ± 0.2 m a⁻¹) between 1935 and 2022. The retreat of Gangotri Glacier decreased from 2001 to 2006 (7.0 ± 4.0 m a⁻¹) compared to the previous observation (1980–2001; 21.0 ± 1.2 m a⁻¹) but increased about three times between 2006 and 2017 (21.9 ± 1.9 m a⁻¹). Furthermore, from 2017 to 2022, the frontal retreat accelerated by about 1.5 times (33.8 ± 6.7 m a⁻¹) compared to the period between 2006 and 2017. The findings of the present study are consistent with ground-based survey conducted by the Geological Survey of India” (Bhambri et al., 2023). Rawat and Singh, 2023, used the “manual digitization of different Landsat images marking of place ... During the study period (1993–2021), the cumulative retreat of the glacier was measured to be 1,850 m, and the average rate of glacier retreat was 61.66 m/year”. Thakur et al., 2023, considered “multi-sensor data from 2017 to 2021 to demonstrate the rapid transformation of the Gomukh ... Between 2017 and 2021, the Gangotri Glacier’s frontal zone underwent rapid changes, including the formation and merging of ephemeral lakes, the development of ice cliffs, and a shift in the meeting of melt streams from Raktvarn Glacier. ... During the investigation period, the snout of the Gangotri Glacier has receded by around 270 m”. That is, a quite large retreat.

Let us return to the Google Earth images. In <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gomukh>, the coordinates of Gomukh are: DMS 30°55'36"N 79°4'51"E, Decimal 30.926667, 79.080833.

Discussion

In 2017, to obtain the Figure 4 proposed there, I superimposed the two Google Earth satellite images of 2010 and 2016. The positions of the terminus in 2010 and 2016 were given by two red lines manually drawn. A reference point in the two images was used for measurements. Thanks to the image scale, we found two+ distances, and evaluated a retreat of 150 ± 20 meters, corresponding to a rate of 25 ± 4 meters per year. I used a reference point, because in 2017, I observed a relevant shift of the image, when I changed from 2010 to 2016 in the time series. Today, 2024, the shift is negligible.

To understand how the retreat rate had been evaluated in 2017, let us consider the upper part of the following Figure 1. In the left panel, the reader can find the reference point and the pin of Figure 4, 2017 (pin here represented by a small yellow ellipse). By means of the Google Earth ruler tool, we can find 318 m as distance. Let us add a further pin, here labelled “2010”: the distance changes into 310 m. Then, let us assume an uncertainty of the distance of about ± 10 m. The same we assume for the distance (460 m) of the terminus as in 2016 (right panel of the Figure 1, upper part). We have an uncertainty of the distance difference of about ± 20 m, in the direction considered for evaluating the retreat of the terminus. The retreat rate is given as $(460 - 310) / 6 = 25$ m/yr. The uncertainty of this rate is about ± 4 m/yr. It means that values *from 21 to 29 m/yr* must be considered as representative of the retreat rate I proposed in 2017. Yousuf et al., 2024, say that “manual

derivation of retreat rates using the same Google Earth images ($16.62 \pm 13.02 \text{ m a}^{-1}$) confirm relatively low glacier retreat rate during this period” (Yousuf et al., 2024). My approach is a manual approach too. The values given by Yousuf et al. are ranging from 2.6 to 29.6 m/yr: my representative interval is therefore within Yousuf and coworkers’ interval.

Fig. 1: On the left, a part of the terminus of Gangotri in 2010, on the right, a part of the terminus in 2016. Images courtesy Google Earth, Maxar Technologies (left), CNES/Airbus (right). Tools courtesy Google Earth.

Therefore, the direction given in the Figure 1 (upper part) seems being representative of the larger local retreat of the Gomukh. As told by Yousuf and coworkers “differences [in the evaluation of the retreat rate] are mainly due to the data/approaches/observational period considered in these studies”. The fact that the retreat rate given by Yousuf and coworkers is ranging from 2.6 to 29.6 m/yr, is evidencing that the researchers considered a front of the glacier, which is wider than the portion I considered in 2017. For instance, in the lower part of the Figure 1, let us add a second pin “2010” and a second direction. In this selected direction, it seems the terminus moved about 50 m. It means that the retreat rate is about 8 m/yr.

Yousuf and coworkers do not show the terminus they considered on the Google Earth images of 2010 and 2016; for this reason, any further comparison is not possible.

As previously told, the shift of Google Earth images is today negligible. Therefore, we could use the terminus of 2010, as we can observe in the image of 2010, manually marked by the “a” pins, and the terminus of 2016 marked by the “b” pins as in the Figure 2, and evaluate a set of distances (without the need of a reference point). The choice of the pins a-b pairs is influencing the result. Moreover, the choice of the positions of “b”

pins could be debatable. Today, Google Earth is proposing further images in the time series. We have the possibility to use the 2017 Google Earth image as in the following Fig. 3. The terminus is manually evidenced by “c” pins. We can choose five pairs and evaluate the distances between “a” and “c” pins (see Appendix for further discussion). Using the arithmetic mean of the distances, we find a retreat rate of 23.5 ± 3.9 m/yr.

Fig.2: This is a detail of Google Earth 2016 image, where we have manually described the terminus by “b” pins. Pins “a” are describing the terminus in 2010. The shift of Google Earth images is today negligible and therefore we can use the two sets of pins, without any reference point. Image courtesy Google Earth, CNES/Airbus. Tools courtesy Google Earth.

Fig.3: This image is showing the terminus of Gangotri Glacier in 2017. In the case that we consider the pins in the figure (“a” and “c”), we can evaluate a set of distances. Using the arithmetic mean of the distances corresponding to the five red lines, the resulting retreat rate is 23.5 ± 3.9 m/yr. Image courtesy Google Earth and CNES/Airbus. Tools courtesy Google Earth.

In conclusion, in the case that we use the “a” pins and the “c” pins in the Figure 3, as representative of the Gomukh terminus, the retreat rate turns out to be 23.5 ± 3.9 m/yr, corresponding to an interval of values from 19.6 to 27.4 m/yr. These values can be considered representative of local larger retreats of the Gomukh. In the case that a wider Gomukh profile is assumed for evaluating the retreat, the mean rate changes. Since Yousuf and coworkers do not show the terminus that they considered on Google Earth images, any further comparison is not possible. However, we can tell that our rate interval (19.6 to 27.4 m/yr), is in the range from 2.6 to 29.6 m/yr given by Yousuf and coworkers. Let us stress that our interval has been evaluated by 2010 and 2017 images, whereas the interval provided by Yousuf et al., by 2010 and 2016 images.

For the discussion previously given, we used the images of 9/25/2010, 11/28/2016 and 10/7/2017, provided by Google Earth Pro. Besides these images, the proposed time series includes further images of 2018, 2019, 2021 and 2022. Here in the following Figs. 6 and 7, the terminus in 2019 and 2022 is given. Further studies are therefore possible, to evaluate the retreat rate from 2017 to 2022.

Fig.4: The terminus of Gangotri in 2019. The pins are the same as those in the Figure 3.

Fig.5: The terminus of Gangotri in 2022. The pins are the same as those in the Figure 3. Image courtesy Google Earth and CNES/Airbus. Tools courtesy Google Earth.

We owe a huge thank you to the Google Earth Pro service for satellite images and tools provided for the manual analysis of the retreat of Gangotri Gomukh. Here we used images and tools for research and education purposes, according to the guidelines at <https://about.google/brand-resource-center/products-and-services/geo-guidelines/> (“Google Earth or Earth Studio can be used for purposes such as research, education, film and nonprofit use without needing permission”).

Appendix

In the Figure 3 we have proposed a possible choice of pin-pairs to determine the distances and consequently the retreat rate. In fact, the red lines resemble the ribs of a hand fan. The reason of the fan-shape measurement approach, given in Fig.3, is in the natural evolution of the glacier, which shows the development of circular crevasses, as given in the following sequence of Google Earth satellite images.

Fig. A1: The panels are proposing Google Earth images of (a) October 2012 (courtesy Maxar Technologies), (b) October 2017 (courtesy CNES/Airbus), (c) November 2018 (courtesy Maxar Technologies), and (d) October 2019 (courtesy Maxar Technologies). Note the evolution of the circular crevasses on the right part of images.

In any case, the “fan-shape” approach could be debatable. So let us further discuss how can we calculate the retreat rate of the terminus. In Yousuf et al., 2024, the researchers say that “The retreat was calculated in terms of length change along the glacier front and along the central flowline. For frontal retreat estimation, lines with 60 m distance were drawn parallel to the central flowline and the average distance between two consecutive glacier outlines was measured from the intersections of the parallel lines”.

To follow this approach, first we must establish the flowline. Let us use Google Earth image of October 2012 (courtesy Maxar Technologies), the pins we have already used in the Figure 3, and two “F” pins to indicate the central flowline. Please consider that here we are just showing the method, and therefore the positions of F pins can be debatable. Let us apply GIMP software to have a grid and parallel white lines. For the sake of simplicity, only four lines are shown in the following Fig.A1.

Fig. A1: In the two images we have considered the satellite image of October 2012, courtesy Google Earth and Maxar Technologies. See please the text for explanation of the right panel.

Using the distances between pin-pairs on the white parallel lines we find a mean distance of 212 ± 40 m, corresponding to a retreat rate of 30 ± 6 m/yr. Of course, we have considered only a part of the terminus. Moreover, the result is depending on the choice of F pair.

Another possibility is to use the Fréchet distance. Let us consider an intuitive definition of it, as in [Wikipedia](#): “the Fréchet distance is a measure of similarity between curves that takes into account the location and ordering of the points along the curves”. “Imagine a person traversing a finite curved path while walking the dog on a leash, with the dog traversing a separate finite curved path. Each can vary their speed to keep slack in the leash, but neither can move backwards. The Fréchet distance between the two curves is the length of the shortest leash sufficient for both to traverse their separate paths from start to finish. Note that the definition is symmetric with respect to the two curves”. See please also the illustration given by Hu and Yao (2021), who proposed the evaluation of this distance for investigating glaciers in the west Tibet. Empirically, we can imagine the Fréchet distance as the minimum possible length of the “leash” of a dog moving along curve “c” while the human moves along curve “a”, both in the same direction. However, to obtain a measure and its uncertainty, regarding the retreat of the glacier terminus, is less intuitive and requires some experimentation.

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